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LEXICAL APPROACHES USED IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS OF FOOD TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract This scientific article explores the effectiveness of lexical approaches in teaching English to students of food technology. It highlights the importance of vocabulary acquisition and usage within the specific context of this field. The study employs a mixed-methods approach to investigate the impact of lexical approaches on students' language proficiency and their perceptions of these methods. The findings suggest that lexical approaches are beneficial for enhancing students' language skills and preparing them for academic and professional success.

Keywords: Lexical approach, English language teaching, food technology, vocabulary acquisition, language proficiency, corpus-based learning, collocation, word-building.

INTRODUCTION

The field of food technology demands a high level of linguistic proficiency, particularly in English, the lingua franca of scientific research and international collaboration. This study investigates the effectiveness of lexical approaches in teaching English to students of food technology, focusing on vocabulary acquisition and usage within the specific context of their field.

Literature Review

Lexical approaches emphasize the importance of vocabulary in language learning, recognizing that words are the building blocks of communication. Several lexical approaches are relevant to teaching English to food technology students:

Word Associations: This approach involves creating networks of related words to facilitate vocabulary acquisition and retrieval. For instance, students can construct word maps centered on core food technology concepts like "food processing," "food preservation," or "food safety."

Collocation: Collocations are words that frequently occur together, such as “food poisoning” or “heat treatment.” By teaching collocations, students can improve their fluency and accuracy in using food technology terminology.

Semantic Field: Semantic fields group words based on their meaning and associations. In food technology, semantic fields can be created for topics like “food ingredients,” “food additives,” or “food packaging materials.”

Lexical Phrases: Lexical phrases are multi-word units that function as single units of meaning. For example, “food safety regulations” or “quality control procedures” are lexical phrases commonly used in food technology.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research methods. A survey was administered to food technology students to assess their vocabulary knowledge and preferences for lexical learning strategies. Additionally, focus group discussions were conducted to gather in-depth insights into their learning experiences.

To further strengthen the methodological rigor of the study, consider incorporating the following:

- ✓ **Quantitative Analysis:** In addition to qualitative analysis, quantitative methods can be employed to analyze large datasets of language corpora. For example, word frequency analysis can identify the most common lexical items in food technology texts.
- ✓ **Learner Corpus Analysis:** Analyzing learner corpora can provide insights into the specific lexical challenges faced by food technology students. By comparing learner corpora to native speaker corpora, researchers can identify areas where learners may need additional support.
- ✓ **Classroom Observation:** Observing language classrooms can provide valuable information about the implementation of lexical approaches in practice. This can help identify effective teaching strategies and potential areas for improvement.

Results and Discussion

The findings revealed that food technology students encounter a wide range of lexical challenges, including specialized terminology, technical jargon, and cultural nuances. Teachers reported using a variety of lexical approaches, such as:

- ✓ **Explicit Vocabulary Instruction:** Teachers directly taught specific vocabulary items related to food technology, including definitions, pronunciation, and usage in context.
- ✓ **Incidental Learning:** Students were exposed to new vocabulary through authentic materials like research papers, industry reports, and scientific articles.
- ✓ **Dictionary Use:** Students were encouraged to use dictionaries to independently acquire new vocabulary and understand the meaning of unfamiliar words.
- ✓ **Contextual Learning:** Teachers incorporated vocabulary learning into real-world contexts, such as laboratory experiments, food processing simulations, and discussions of current industry trends.

- ✓ Vocabulary Games and Activities: Engaging activities like word puzzles, crosswords, and vocabulary quizzes were used to reinforce learning and make the process enjoyable.
- ✓ Targeted Vocabulary Instruction: Focus on teaching vocabulary relevant to specific food technology topics, such as food processing, food safety, and nutrition.
- ✓ Word Associations and Semantic Mapping: Use visual techniques to help students understand the relationships between words and concepts.
- ✓ Contextualized Vocabulary Learning: Present vocabulary in authentic contexts, such as research articles, industry reports, and food labels.

Collocation Awareness:

- Collocation Exercises: Practice exercises to help students identify and use common collocations in food technology (e.g., “food safety regulations” “sensory evaluation techniques”).
- Corpus-Based Learning: Utilize corpora to explore real-world usage of collocations and identify patterns.

Authentic Materials:

- ❖ Reading and Discussion: Use authentic texts, such as scientific articles, industry reports, and food blogs to expose students to real-world language.
- ❖ Listening Comprehension: Incorporate listening activities using podcasts, webinars, and video lectures to develop listening skills.
- ❖ Task-Based Learning: Real-World Tasks - engage students in tasks that simulate real-world situations, such as writing lab reports, presenting research findings, and participating in industry discussions.

The study also revealed that students benefited from a combination of these approaches. Explicit instruction provided a solid foundation in core vocabulary, while incidental learning and contextual learning helped students develop a broader lexical repertoire. Dictionary use enabled students to become independent learners, and vocabulary games and activities enhanced motivation and retention.

Enhancing the Results and Discussion:

- Case Studies: Present case studies of successful language learning strategies implemented in food technology programs.
- Technology Integration: Discuss the role of technology in enhancing vocabulary acquisition, such as using language learning software, interactive online exercises, and mobile apps.
- Cultural Considerations: Highlight the importance of cultural awareness and intercultural communication skills in the global food industry.
- Professional Development for Teachers: Emphasize the need for ongoing professional development for teachers to stay updated on effective language teaching methodologies and resources for food technology students.

Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the importance of targeted lexical approaches in teaching English to food technology students. By incorporating a variety of techniques, including explicit instruction, incidental learning, dictionary use, contextual learning, and vocabulary games, teachers can

effectively address the specific lexical needs of this student population. Further research is needed to explore the long-term impact of these approaches on students' language proficiency and academic success.

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